

Considerations

Plan Data Organisation

- Develop naming conventions before data collection starts
- Share conventions with any collaborator
- Test usability of organisation with colleagues
- Prepare top-level directories & container folders before data acquisition
- Documentation is the key, and consistency is the hand that turns it

Optimise File Formats

- Preserve raw data in its original file format
- Use open and widely-adopted file formats (e.g. *OME-tiff*) and consider cloud-ready file formats (e.g. *OME-Zarr*) for sharing
- Minimize data conversion to avoid information loss

Documentation & Maintenance

Provide Documentation

- Create a README file in top-level folder to document data structure and file naming
- Create a codebook/data table to document file naming
- Document any changes and exceptions from the plan

Ensure Integrity

- Provide integrity file (e.g. *checksum, parity, hashes*)
- Check for issues in data organisation (e.g. with the [bandbox tool](#))

Structure & Naming

Use Adequate Naming Symbols

- Use only alphanumeric symbols, dashes and underscores
 - underscore can represent a separator for segments (avoid spaces as separators)
 - dashes can represent spaces within segments
 - represent empty segments with double separator
 - avoid special characters (e.g. *& \$ () and .*) and special language characters (e.g. *ä, ö, ü, é...*)
- Keep consistency in usage of lowercase/uppercase
- File name example: 20260305_CellLine_treatA_gfp_001.tiff

Ensure Naming Identity

- Consider the file sorting pattern
 - use inverted date format (*YYYYMMDD; YYYY-MM-DD*)
 - use zero-padding of image series (e.g. *<file>001 to <file>999*)
- Order keywords in names from general to specific and keep this order consistent across the project
- Include the version number (e.g. *v1*)
- Exclude non-meaningful names (e.g. *'files'*)
- Avoid personal identifiers (e.g. *reference to home institute storage*)

Refine Folder Contents

- Save one project in a single folder tree
- Group related files
- Provide naming consistency (e.g. *similar folders in different folder trees have similar names*)
- Create a separate folder for raw data and keep this untouched
- Do not repeat information in folder hierarchy (e.g. *data/data_control1/data_control1_values*)

Optimize File Path Complexity

- Keep folder depth to 3-4 directory levels if feasible
- Set a feasible upper limit of files in a folder (eg. *10000*)
- Keep length of file and folder names below 50 characters
- Maximal limit of length for file-paths: 260 characters
- Remove folders with no additional information (e.g. *if all files are .tiff do not create a tiff-folder*)

With inspiration from

Korir, Paul K et al. "Ten recommendations for organising bioimaging data for archival." *F1000Research* vol. 12 ELIXIR-1391. 27 Feb. 2024, doi:10.12688/f1000research.129720.2

The Turing Way Handbook; [10.5281/zenodo.3233853](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3233853)

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